

Questionnaire

Introductory Section

Welcome to Values in Agile Software Development study. We investigate and get insights into the values considered in agile software development in IT organizations.

Researchers: Hidden for double-blind revision

Purpose of the research study: We are interested in collecting some research data about your personal value at work. In addition, we are interested in how you practice organization and social sustainability values in relation to agile. The purpose of the study is to understand more about the role of human, organization, and social sustainability values in agile software development in an IT organization. This research consists of answering an entry survey.

Time duration for this questionnaire: 30-40 minutes — the survey is composed of 7 sections, including this consent form in the beginning and submission form in the end.

Survey Design: Filling out this survey via a desktop or a laptop is highly recommended.

Types of data: We are using standard survey instruments from validated research, which have been developed under rigorous quality assurance and are reliable. Your textual entries are super insightful and will be handled with adequate care. If you disclose any personal details that could identify you, we will not quote them in any way that could reveal your identity as a study participant. Our recommendation is to just not name specific individuals' names in your entries.

Potential risks and discomforts: For the data collection, your data will be anonymous. The risks of participating in this study are minimal. However, there is a small risk of inadvertent disclosure from your text answers. In addition, the study findings may be disclosed through legal action - when, for example, non-disclosure would constitute contempt of court. However, as far as possible, we will ensure that any such disclosure is unlikely.

Potential benefits for participants and society: By filling out the entry survey and participating in this study, you get a reflection of your personal values, organization, and social sustainability values related to agile software development. The project will provide an opportunity to all participants to examine and read our findings, if desired.

Payment for participation: You will not be paid for participating in this study.

Identification of investigators: If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact us.

Signature of research subject: I understand the procedures and conditions of my participation described above. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form. By clicking 'Next', I agree to the procedures and conditions.

We follow standard ethics procedures at (Hidden for double-blind revision). By acknowledging below and clicking 'Next', you agree to participate in this study. You can withdraw at any time.

Section 2 | Demographic

The questions in this section are used for determining the **general characteristics** of the survey participant.

- What is your age?
- How would you describe your gender identity? (e.g. Male, Female, Non-Binary, Prefer not to answer, etc)
- What is your current job title?
- How many years of your experience is related to software development?
- How many years of your experience in agile?
- How many years have you worked for this organization?

Section 3 | Work Values related with Agile Software Development (Values Q-Sort)

This question uses the Values Q-Sort approach to determine your **work values**:

1. Open the Miro Board link on your email.
2. Follow the instructions on the Miro Board.
3. Provide the link to the Miro board after you finish.

Question List

- Link to Miro Board

Section 4 | Work Values in Agile Practices

This section is used to determine **how the work values are considered** in the agile software development practices.

1. Look at your Most Preferred Statement from Values Q-Sort.
2. Answer the questions below.
 - What is your interpretation about the Most Preferred statement?
 - Why did you choose it as the Most Preferred statement?
 - Based on your experience, does the Most Preferred statement influence your decisions and practices in agile software development? If yes, how? If not, why not?
 - Do you use any specific tools or frameworks which help to reflect about the Most Preferred statement into your day-to-day agile software development? If yes, which ones?
 - In which agile ceremonies and/or artifacts do you consider the Most Preferred statement?
 - Product Inception (Ceremony)
 - Backlog Grooming/Refinement (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Planning (Ceremony)
 - Daily (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Review (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Retrospective (Ceremony)
 - Product Backlog (Artifact)
 - Sprint Backlog (Artifact)
 - Burndown Chart (Artifact)
 - Definition of Done (Artifact)

- Product Increment (Artifact)
- Others

Section 5 | Organization Values in Agile Practices

This section is used to determine **how the organization values are considered** in the agile software development practices.

1. Read the definitions of organizational values.
2. Answer the questions below.

- Based on your experience, do you see any of the organization values reflected in day-to-day agile software development? If yes, how? If not, why not?
- (If Yes) Do you use any specific tools or frameworks that help to reflect the organization values into your day-to-day agile software development? If yes, which ones?
- In which agile ceremonies and/or artifacts do you consider the organization values?
 - Product Inception (Ceremony)
 - Backlog Grooming/Refinement (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Planning (Ceremony)
 - Daily (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Review (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Retrospective (Ceremony)
 - Product Backlog (Artifact)
 - Sprint Backlog (Artifact)
 - Burndown Chart (Artifact)
 - Definition of Done (Artifact)
 - Product Increment (Artifact)
 - Others

Section 6 | Social Sustainability Values in Agile Practices

This section is used to determine **how the social sustainability values** are considered in the agile software development practices.

1. Read the definitions of Social Sustainability Values
2. Answer the questions below

[List of Social Sustainability Values Definition]

- Based on your experience, do you see any of the social sustainability values above reflected in your day-to-day agile software development? If yes, how? If not, why not?
- (If Yes) Do you use any specific tools or frameworks that help to reflect about the social sustainability values into your day-to-day agile software development? If yes, which ones?
- In which agile ceremonies and/or artifacts do you consider the social sustainability values?
 - Product Inception (Ceremony)
 - Backlog Grooming/Refinement (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Planning (Ceremony)
 - Daily (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Review (Ceremony)
 - Sprint Retrospective (Ceremony)
 - Product Backlog (Artifact)
 - Sprint Backlog (Artifact)
 - Burndown Chart (Artifact)
 - Definition of Done (Artifact)
 - Product Increment (Artifact)
 - Others

Section 7 | Submission

Thank you for participating in our survey. We really appreciate your answer. Please submit this form if you have finished.